

Life-long learning program
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OIKODOMOS

Consolidation and expansion of a Virtual Campus

WORKPACKAGE 4
EXPANDING LEARNING ACTIVITIES TO NON ACADEMIC ENVIRONMENTS

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This is a report of the activities carried out in WP 4 during the implementation of the learning programme: the dissemination of projects produced by students, international exhibitions in Grenoble, Bratislava and Famagusta, association of professionals and citizens to debates, participatory actions and definition and design of learning modules.

2. INITIAL CONCEPT AND ACTION OF THE WORKPROGRAM

To expand learning activities to larger audience inside and outside the academic context, the WP 4 proposes to display results of the OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus at each community level by different means: Joint exhibitions of international workshops projects, debates and participatory actions with citizens and professionals, preparation of learning communities and pedagogic supports for permanent education in Housing.

Joint exhibitions presenting projects carried out by students in four common international workshops (Ghent, Grenoble, Bratislava, Istanbul) were presented by project partners in order to inform new students, researchers, practitioners about the learning supports for study and work on Housing themes and to contribute to gain the feed-back from administrators and citizens. Primarily of interest to students, teachers or professionals, the program proposed events and spaces of interaction on-line and/or on-site with the general public. Information engaging neighbours in their living environment were used to show the interest to mix and enrich it with blended activities on the OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus ICT platform.

A module with learning content of Housing suited to non academic learners was prepared for testing by potential learning communities in the field of architecture and urban planning.

The cooperation between different partner schools participating to the OIKODOMOS project consortium and their coordinated action illustrated the apport of the European vision of contemporary housing and the interest for exchanges in the context of larger partnership and blended learning.

3. APPROACH

The WP 4 consisted of a series of coordinated activities, organized around the main event / deliverable which is the Exhibition, displaying projects and activities developed in the partners schools and common workshops. The purpose was to establish a direct contact with external partners, citizens, local authorities, practitioners, where the OIKODOMOS students projects were carried out (Ghent, Bratislava, Grenoble, Gazimagusa) in order to discover results and functions of design studios, Virtual Campus workspaces and repositories.

To reinforce the dissemination effect, exhibitions were prepared with the participation of external extra-academic partners, selected by organizing schools in each city/site.

As anticipated in the original action plan, exchanges with prior non-academic partners and feedback from participants in the discussions were used to assess the needs and expectations of the potential public interested in the new modular blended learning. An educational concept developed from past

experiences and an experimental prototype of teaching units on Urban Housing (Housing Learning Module) was designed and suitable for integration with the Virtual Campus OIKODOMOS Workspaces.

According to the contract, 4 categories of actions were developed in this work package WP4 with their corresponding deliverables:

- D9 Exhibition Bratislava (Slovakia)
- D10 Exhibition Grenoble(France)
- D11 Exhibition Gazimagusa (North Cyprus)
- D12 Housing Learning Module
- D13 Learning Communities
- D14 Participatory actions

4. EXHIBITIONS

Conceived as an "event", the exhibitions provided information on the production of joint workshops and the features of the Virtual Campus, generating contacts and reactions to feedback from visitors. Exhibitions were also used as reference points and sources for other complementary actions of the OIKODOMOS program dissemination to the public: professional associations, elected officials and citizen groups involved in local projects of urban development and housing.

The coordination of the actions in WP4 participating schools has added a European dimension to local contacts, especially through the use of ICT as a means of simultaneous exchanges with distant sites and associated partners in other countries.

Thus the use of video conferencing involved Grenoble to attend openings of Bratislava exhibitions and discussions with Slovak architects. The presence of students from Sint Lucas, URL-La Salle, IUG, FASTU and EMU at the exhibition and the workshop organized in Istanbul by EMU has also established interesting cultural and professional exchanges. Information about exhibitions and debates disseminated on partners "OIKOBlogs" (see WP 2) to strengthen this dimension.

The exhibitions were built around some local themes or challenges treated in workshops and able to facilitate understanding of presented results and illustrate the OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus functionality. They were proposed to serve as a primer to dialog with non-academic audiences on issues of their interest and estimate their needs in lifelong learning and ability to form specific Learning Communities. All partner schools have also been involved in several Participatory actions combining in varying degrees the academic public, architects, planners, citizens or residents' associations.

Initially, exhibitions were programmed in cities-supports of joint workshops involving mixed teams of students from each school. Projects developed in the studios, having been inspired by the local site development challenges, exhibitions played the role of catalisator facilitating exchanges and interactions with the extra-academic audiences, by referring to a locally known context.

The exhibition concept was developed on four additional sub-themes:

- Projects produced in studios-workshops on the local site issues¹,
- Similar projects developed by students in other cities, to illustrate the interest of a wider European approach.
- Presentation of the ICT Virtual Campus platform and functions which served as support for workshops preparation and activities. Exhibitions have included several open sessions exploring OIKODOMOS Workspaces and Case Repository platforms, tutored by teachers, or pre-recorded demonstration program.
- Diffusion on screen and/or video projectors of some 300 selected projects produced on platform OIKODOMOS or in joint workshops, to illustrate the richness and variety of documents and learning outcomes.

¹ Projects displayed in exhibitions were selected from five thematic common workshops : Ghent (Dwelling and life-long Sustainability), Grenoble (Housing for Diversity), Bratislava (Effective Housing) and Istanbul (Housing and Proximity)

OIKODOMOS: WORKSPACES No workspace active

Workshop Bratislava : Effective Housing

Date Start: 09 June 2009 Date End: 31 December 2009

Bratislava workshop (14-20th of October 2009) implies the experiences from previous Oikodomos workshops in Ghent (Lifelong dwelling) and Grenoble (Housing for diversity). It formulates the Effective urban and housing development in the suburban part of Bratislava corresponding to: site specifics; connections to the city context; life styles and situations; constructions and materials; low energy and eco friendly design; appropriate density; public spaces and amenities, etc. Moreover the site is situated in the impressive natural environment, which supports the principles of garden city design and the diffusion of natural and residential structures.

Preparatory stage of the workshop (June – October 2009) is fixed to develop joint learning activities of the partners based on the „Workspace“ virtual learning space.

The aim of the workshop is to develop conceptual proposals for the Bratislava site on the international and interdisciplinary platform and looking for general models of effective housing design on urban and architectural levels.

More info, Site presentation

Institutions participating in this workspace:

FA STU, URL - La Salle, IUG, Sint Lucas, Others, --

Relevant deliverables:

Workshop Grenoble: Housing for diversity

Date Start: 13 February 2009 Date End: 28 April 2009

This workshop is built on the previous workshop experience in Ghent (October, 2008) and integrates 3 complementary learning activities:

- A period of preparation based on a "virtual" design studio, using as a pedagogic support the Oikodomos Workspaces.

- A project studio « in situ » gathering student's and teachers in common workshop teamwork and activities in Grenoble (22-28th of April 2009).

- A period of exploitation, capitalizing workshop activities and students' projects in partner Schools teaching programmes and uploading results on the Oikodomos : Workspaces.

The site chosen for this workshop is located in Grenoble central urban area. The scientific peninsula urban project called "GIANT" covering 250 ha of existing enclosed land including scientific utilities, research centers, schools of engineers has to be transformed into livable district welcoming new diversified populations and urban activities. [+info](#)

Institutions participating in this workspace:

FA STU, IUG, Sint Lucas, URL - La Salle, KataliSys, --

Relevant deliverables:

Figure 1. Workspaces: projects selected from workshops in the Virtual Campus.

A common documentary "Exhibition support kit" was developed and proposed by IUG to all partners opening local exhibition almost simultaneously. It contains:

- Common announcement flyers and signs, customizable in local language,
- General introduction to exhibitions,
- OIKODOMOS project and ICT platforms presentation poster ²,
- Selection of pertinent teamwork posters related to workshops Ghent, Grenoble, Bratislava and Istanbul,
- PowerPoint presentations of two slideshows (80 and 300 projects extracted from workspaces),
- Photomontage of « workshop atmosphere » with students' portraits to use for graphic animation of complementary displays.

² Provided by La-Salle team

Figure 2. Common flyers, template for local adaptations

Exhibitions, generally accompanied by debates were presented usually in different complementary sites in each city and associated with specific events co-organized with local partners for citizens and extra-academic audience. Exhibitions provided support for additional participatory actions or an introduction to learning communities' identification and setting.

Two videoconferences have allowed a remote virtual participation of distant partner universities in order to demonstrate the flexibility of the ICT tools used to supplement the Virtual Campus. In addition, coordinated OIKOblogs disseminated information on different events and exhibitions proposed by each school.³

Figure 3. OIKOblogs Grenoble and Bratislava presenting exhibitions

³ The OIKOblogs were set up by La Salle and USI and are introduced in the report of WP 2.

During the period of project preparation the initial choice of the city of Barcelona as a support for an exhibition was abandoned in favour of sites in Istanbul and Famagusta, managed by new partners from EMU North Cyprus due to better alignment of projects produced in workshops over local issues.

Finally, exhibitions were displayed between February and October 2011 in Bratislava, Grenoble, Istanbul and Famagusta. Some selected elements⁴ from the Exhibition kit were transmitted to Brussels OIKODOMOS Final Conference organisers and displayed in Sint Lucas School of Architecture entrance hall.

4.1 Bratislava exhibitions

FASTU organized three public exhibitions presenting projects from OIKODOMOS workshop studios. Exhibitions at community and city level, displaying the projects produced by students, contributed to gain feedback from administrators and citizens. The exhibitions were planned in order to broaden the awareness of the project activities among wider public. They were realized at the public places of the city respectively district centres. The exposure was through the printed posters, invitations, newspapers, web publications and personnel invitations. During the exhibitions and vernisages were accomplished the presentations of the project activities. Visitors could express their comments and ideas through the blank books and open discussions. Long distance presentation of the partner (IUG) was integrated through the videoconference.

Professionals in architecture and urban planning⁵ in charge of the Master Plan amendments and upgrading of urban study, particularly appreciated interesting inspirations from international students works and their multicultural views on the housing development strategies in the locality. During exhibitions, it were also implemented local participatory actions in mixed academic (FASTU) and non-academic settings (local and city administration, citizens, experts) which interweaved local community actions at the neighbourhood/district /city level. Citizens living in the Dubravka neighbourhood were very vivid and active in the discussions on local projects and OIKODOMOS, initiated by exhibitions.

Public Exhibition 15.02. – 01.03.2011, Cultural House Dúbravka, Ozvoldíkova street, Bratislava⁶

With the support of Bratislava-Dubravka Municipality a range of selected student posters and models of the Big Camp area was specifically commented among other projects from Virtual Campus. They were considered with the interest of academics, as well as non-academics – Dubravka citizens and elected members.

Figure 4-5. Presentation by the Mayor of Dubravka

⁴ Posters and workshops presentation slideshow

⁵ e.g. Architectural Agency Krampl, members of Municipality Planning department

⁶ Curators and organizers of the exhibition: FA STU and Local Council Bratislava Dúbravka

Presented projects and discussions conferred a lot of inspirations for the official urban study executor, architect Krampfl. Student works verifying different possibilities and various forms of development on the site were appreciated for their original youthful inventions and ideals. For the Dubravka District Municipality, the exhibition presents a helpful input for on-going elaboration of the urban documentation of such type and size. Exhibition and Virtual Campus sources motivated citizens interest for local participatory actions. As a part of shared learning process students received and welcomed comments from the practitioners, citizens and local elected officials on their projects.

Figures 6-7. Exhibitions in Bratislava-Dubravka City Hall and. Gallery

The exhibition led to many interesting exchanges between participants from diverse audiences.⁷ A local media press and audiovisual coverage disseminated information about this event.⁸

Public Exhibition 04.03. – 18.03.2011, Saratovská street, Gallery Villa Rustica, Bratislava

A second edition of the OIKODOMOS exhibition has been organized for larger local public in order to initiate open debates about the digital learningplatform and the multicultural dimension of the project. Citizens expressed their interest in discovery of architectural and planning design process, tools and presentations of the designed locality in the city district. Open debates occurred with the Municipality elected members.⁹ As for the first exhibition, national and local media informed about the event.

Public Exhibition 29.06– 15.07.2011, Gallery of Architecture SAS (Slovak Architects Society), Balassa palace, Panská street, Bratislava Centre¹⁰

The exhibition was re-installed in June and July 2011 in the public Gallery of Architecture at the Association of Slovak Architects SAS in Balassa palace in historical centre of Bratislava. A smaller replica of the exhibition was presented in September 2011 at the international workshop and Summer school at FA STU. The presented works were completed by the works of the students from the Institute of Town Planning at FA STU.

The aim of this event was to confront the OIKODOMOS project activities and the internationally solved proposals for Big Camp locality at the expert and public level. Exhibition displayed students projects

⁷ Local Council Dúbravka, Mayor and elected members (cca 10), citizens (cca 100), experts - (Dúbravka, Department of the spatial planning, Architectural office Krampfl, SAS – Slovak Architects Society, FA STU students (cca 45) and professors (7)

⁸ Local TV channel (Dúbravka TV), press (Dúbravka newspaper, ARCH – architectural journal, Hospodarske noviny). The exhibition was advertised in local and national newspapers, web portals, posters.

⁹ Audience and participants : FASTU Dean, Dubravka Mayor, members of local council (10), citizens (cca 100), experts from District Spatial planning dept, Arichetcural Agency, SAS, Students (cca 45), academics (7), media (Dubravka newspaper, ARCH magazine, TV Dubravka)

¹⁰ Organizers of the exhibition: Viera Joklova (FA STU), Zuzana Aufrichtova (Local Council Bratislava Dúbravka)

elaborated in OIKODOMOS joint international workshops, specifically focused on effective housing at the Bratislava-Big Camp site .

A long distance videoconference associating French project partner – IUG Grenoble, emphasized the European dimension of the project. Open debates about the multicultural platform shared the OIKODOMOS experiences. Citizens expressed interest in the architectural and planning design process and presentations of the designed locality in the city district. Open debates with the experts, local administration and citizens mixed the academic and non-academic audiences.¹¹

Figure 8. Exhibition in SAS Bratislava

Figure 9. Poster for Dubravka project

FA-STU organized a large multimedia dissemination of OIKODOMOS events, through the public media and press, interviews and articles in local audiovisual and printed media, posters, websites and project OIKOblog,¹² Exhibitions played also a role as support for participatory actions in Dubravka continued by the Municipality.

4.2 Grenoble exhibitions

Two exhibitions organized in Grenoble, in the city center and in the Institut d'Urbanisme, offered the opportunity to present and discuss the results of the OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus.

¹¹ Presence on the opening: the Dean of FA STU, Bratislava chief architect, Bratislava City magistrate representatives, Head of Association of Slovak Architects, Dubravka local council members and citizens. A video-conference with IUG Grenoble associated by a virtual way French colleagues to Bratislava OIKODOMOS presentation and the debate with participants.

¹² Video-reportage from exhibition opening (<http://video.sita.sk/videoservis/bratislava-vystava---navrhy-lokality-velka-luka-od-studentov-architektury/19887-play.html...>)

Public Exhibition 31.05. – 22.07.2011, “Se former à l’Urbanisme- Learning Urban Planning”, m’A-Maison de l’architecture de l’Isère, place de Bérulle, Grenoble Centre ¹³

Attached to valorise the architectural and urban culture in its diversity, IUG and Maison de l’Architecture de Grenoble et de l’Isère ¹⁴ proposed a new episode of professional, academic and extra-academic exchanges about the development process for more sustainable cities. Organizers wanted to question contemporary relations between architecture, housing and urban planning and present new learning tools and methods developed by OIKODOMOS.

Figure 10. Flyer for local debate about learning urban housing,

Figure 11. Exhibition gallery in M'A Grenoble

Exhibitions and cafés-debates with architects and citizens presented approaches of urban mutations analysed in students joint workshops and projects conceived on OIKODOMOS workspaces. A selection of teamwork posters elaborated during the Grenoble OIKODOMOS workshop « Housing for diversity » allowed visitors to discover European students studio proposals for Grenoble Giant-Scientific Peninsula district. ¹⁵

Exhibition included slideshows displaying a collection of 300 selected projects extracted from digital workspaces and repositories. Several tutored demonstrations on computers connected to the OIKODOMOS website give an overview of the capabilities and functions of the Virtual Campus.

Debates ¹⁶ and feed-backs from visitors confirmed the importance of linkage to the local context (e.g. Grenoble related projects from workshops), the interest for the compared, cross-cultural European vision of similar urban issues and the learning capitalization and access to information via ICT supports. Despite large texts in French, the general and professional public experienced some difficulties to deal with linguistic barriers (English as the project communication language) and recommend the progressive translation in French. It confirms the priority of OIKODOMOS project to provide adaptations to local languages. ¹⁷

¹³ Organizers of the exhibition: IUG and m’A-Maison de l’Architecture with the patronage of Grenoble Municipality

¹⁴ m’A – Information centre for architecture, planning, urban development, with library and public exhibition showroom. The institution is supported by Grenoble Municipality, Regional Council Rhône-Alpes, Département de l’Isère and industrial sponsors.

¹⁵ A total of approx. 30 citizens, 8 IUG teachers and 5 local architects participated in the inaugural debate about learning. The exhibition of students’ projects and OIKODOMOS workshop projects received in Grenoble city centre inhabitants, tourists and professional visitors for 2 months in June-July 2011.

¹⁶ “L’Urbanisme et sa formation, quels enjeux -Urbanisme and learning, what issues? “, presentation-debate with teachers, planners, architects, 31/05/2011, m’A, place de Berulle, Grenoble. Info on <http://iug-oikodomos.blogspot.com/>

¹⁷ For this purpose, partners completed common exhibition core by posters in local languages, in other WPs Housing Concepts are translated in Spanish, French, Slovak, Flamish and Turkish.

Figure 12. Computer with OIKODOMOS presentation as part of the showroom exhibition

As a complement of the exhibition held in Maison de l'Architecture, IUG contributed to a non-formal, citizen oriented session of participatory debates « Le Café d'Urbanisme » with residents of the new housing eco-district Quartier de Bonne.¹⁸

Figure 13 .Le Café d'Urbanisme, Café Boulevard Gambetta, Grenoble

Public Exhibition IUG, 6.06.2011 – 30.9.2011, Cité des Territoires Grenoble¹⁹

Another public exhibition of teamwork projects produced in OIKODOMOS joint workshops in Ghent (Lifelong dwelling), Grenoble (Housing for Diversity), Bratislava (Efficient Housing) and Istanbul (Housing and Proximity) has been presented in the entrance hall of the IUG building. The exhibition opening session coincided with the reception in IUG of the « Spring research seminar of territorial sciences » hosted on 6 and 7/6/2011 by University research centre PACTE-Territoire.

Tutored demo sessions of OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus workspaces were presented to seminar participants and information uploaded on IUG OIKOBlog (<http://iug-oikodomos.blogspot.com/>.)

During the University examination period and two registration sessions for new applicants, students, teachers, researchers, parents and citizens from neighbourhood urban area Vigny-Musset visited the exhibition and discovered 300 students projects presentation displayed on posters and permanent slideshows. IUG OIKOBlog informed about this open event.

¹⁸ See section 4 Participatory actions

¹⁹ Organizers of the exhibition: IUG OIKODOMOS team with students start-up association URBANBOX.

Urban planners attending the meeting of OPQU (Office Professionnel de Qualification des Urbanistes) in IUG received also the information about OIKODOMOS and visited the exhibition. Professional partners agreed with the idea to experience OIKODOMOS Learning modules²⁰ as a part of possible mixed learning resources for Permanent Education activities in 2011-2012.

Figure 14. Research seminar PACTE-Territoire

Figure 15. Display of projects from the Virtual Campus

A special session organized by IUG students group participating in Istanbul workshop presented to their classmates projects, final outcomes, experience of ICTs and the « atmosphere » of Istanbul multicultural teamwork. Following the meeting, students demanded IUG and University board support for continuation and greater integration of the OIKODOMOS experience and European transnational project workshops in their learning program.²¹

Figure 16. Exhibition poster and IUG students photos with teamwork «atmosphere »

²⁰ e.g. prototype of Housing Learning Module conceived within the WP4

²¹ A total of approx 300 students and teachers, 50 researchers, 20 professionals, 50 citizens from neighbourhood city areas visited the exhibition.

4.3 Istanbul and Famagusta exhibitions

Two exhibitions have been installed in the Istanbul Technical University –with occasion of the international workshop- and in the Eastern Mediterranean University, in North Cyprus.

Public exhibition in Istanbul, 5.05.2011 – 7.05-2011, Istanbul Technical University (ITU)²²

During the joint workshop in Istanbul focused on the theme of « Housing and Proximity », an exhibition of preparatory works produced by students has been installed in the patio gallery of ITU, to be accessible to OIKODOMOS and local students and teachers.

Fig. 17 Students preparatory posters Exhibition in ITU Istanbul -

Fig 18 Workshop flyer for exhibition EMU

Public exhibition in Famagusta, 24.10 – 31.10.2011) EMU Faculty Exhibition room²³

Local OIKODOMOS team organized on the basis of common «exhibition kit» and local examples a presentation of workshop productions from partners universities and from Eastern Mediterranean University, Faculty of Architecture graduate students. The exhibition was held with an introductory and supportive talk of members of HERA_C: Housing Education Research Advisory Centre together with Faculty of Architecture Administration; Dean, Vice-Dean, Departmental Heads; members from Architects' Chambers, and citizens in Huseyin Ateshin Exhibition Room in Gazimagusa, North Cyprus.

²² Organizers : OIKODOMOS workshop tutors EMU Famagusta and Sint Lucas Brussels

²³ Organizers:EMU OIKODOMOS team. Opening session attendance:60 teachers, academics, architects and local personalities, cca 250 visitors for the exhibition duration.

Figure 19. Views and posters from the Exhibition North Cyprus Famagusta

Discussions with participants at the exhibition opening foreshadowed the possibilities to extend the project with the larger audience. The perspective to collaborate with the Chamber of Architects in Cyprus to use the OIKODOMOS web platform as an innovative blended learning of lifelong education meeting point for practising architects, especially due to the new requirement of UIA directives was proposed. Initiation of a lifelong learning program with citizens can be launched as an informal education by the faculty suggested by Faculty Dean. This opportunity will soon be evaluated for further studies within the curriculum in a specialised master program open to the housing sector in the public.

5. PARTICIPATORY ACTIONS

In addition to exhibitions and opening ceremonies, a series of debates was held with visitors and residents. Participants have discussed topics related to local issues developed in OIKODOMOS workshops, or confronted with other similar cases reported in the exhibitions. It served as background to the questions of citizens role in a project, their information and competences and possible training and use of participation tools.

In Bratislava, the treatment of Centre Dubravka has been a central reference to these debates, in Grenoble the site GIANT and Eco-District De Bonne, in Barcelona students experimented the participatory process with residents in Plus Ultra neighbourhood.

The capacity of ICT tools demonstrated by OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus appeared often as interesting advances that can help the efficiency in participation and could empower citizens, local actors and stakeholders.

5.1 Barcelona « Proximity & participation » in Plus Ultra area

La Salle teaching team launched a seminar with integrated participatory process which enabled participating students to explore the role of the architect in the finding of solutions to socially conflictive problems dealing with housing in the contemporary city (See detailed process in Appendix 1). In this participatory process, people got information and thus have the opportunity or the power of dialogue and collaboration, studying and evaluating various alternatives that allow them to negotiate and decide. A participatory process was, therefore, educational and democratic. In this process students-architects played a role of organizer, educator and mediator. The process was documented in the OIKOblog La Salle.²⁴

Posted by: Ángel Martín Etiquetas: participation 0 Comments

Recommend this on Google

THURSDAY, JUNE 23, 2011

SESIÓN DE PARTICIPACIÓN: BARRIO PLUS ULTRA. VIVIENDA

VIVIENDA

Es evidente que el barrio Plus Ultra es completamente diferente al resto de la ciudad, y hemos intentado examinar qué es lo que tiene que hace que lo aprecies tanto. Para averiguar lo que valoráis y estimáis de vuestro barrio, se realizaron varias actividades.

¿Qué creéis que es lo más importante de vuestra vivienda? ¿Qué es mejor en las viviendas existentes en comparación a unas nuevas viviendas?

Figure 20. Participatory process presented in OIKOBlog

Figure 21. Capturing the citizens' impressions in the neighborhood

5.2 Citizens participation in Grenoble and Bratislava

Café d'Urbanisme (28.6.2011), Le Café, Boulevard Gambetta, Grenoble

As a complement of the exhibition in Maison de l'Architecture de Grenoble, IUG co-organized an open, citizen-oriented session of participatory debates, « Le Café d'Urbanisme », with residents of the new housing eco-district Quartier de Bonne. Teachers, architects and urban planners intervened in dialog exploring the citizens' capability to participate on sustainable housing development project. OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus was presented as example of an open source for documentation, learning and potential empowerment of local associations.²⁵ Flyers for visit OIKODOMOS exhibitions in m'A and IUG were distributed with Virtual Campus and OIKOblogs web addresses.

²⁴ <http://lasalle-oikodomos.blogspot.com/>

²⁵ A total of cca 50 citizens, 2 teachers, 3 architects- designers of the district and representatives of 2 neighbourhood associations were involved in this event organized on 28/06/2011.

Figure 22. Images from Café d'urbanisme Grenoble

Figure 23. Flyer OIKODOMOS and Exhibitions

Bratislava-Dubravka (04.03.2011) Saratovská street, Gallery Villa Rustica, Bratislava

Two public meetings with Dúbravka local council members, elected people, students, and citizens confronted local positions on urban housing in the city-centre area, with students projects developed by international teams in OIKODOMOS workshops. Discussions were focused on the topic of Dubravka development perspectives and alternatives proposed in OIKODOMOS projects. The meeting was an opportunity to present case study repository databases available on the Virtual Campus. These information sources were considered as useful tools for improving citizen capability to participate in the public debate and to enlarge the choice of credible development alternatives.

Figures 24-25. Bratislava Dubravka projects and OIKODOMOS presentation in local press

6. LEARNING COMMUNITIES

The aim of this part of work package was to design and implement activities to engage neighbours both in their own living environment and in the activities in the ICT platform (learning communities). The common approach consisted in presenting the compendium of design studios developed during the OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus to local authorities where the projects were developed. Activities were aimed at the general public and local authorities, also of interest to students and to teachers and professionals in the architecture and urban planning.

In Bratislava, activities of FASTU to engage and enhance the learning community of OIKODOMOS virtual campus can be allocated to three levels – internal (within own institution), external (spread to other institutions), and public (involving new local authorities, public).

Project philosophy, experiences, learning platforms and studio works were presented firstly to other colleagues at FASTU, to achieve wider application base. Subsequently the new local authorities were addressed with the information about the integration to the multicultural learning platform, with the usage for the urban design studios at new localities²⁶. The effort for the integration of new learning partners was realized by the presentation of the compendium of design studios, developed up to now, together with the information about the functionalities of the project platforms and the philosophy and experiences with the blended learning in architecture and urban planning.²⁷

In Barcelona, the case of the neighbourhood “Plus Ultra” created a community of practice on the local settlement site. Students and teachers from Arquitectura La Salle worked with the Plus Ultra neighborhood with the objective of building a learning community and help inhabitants to externalize and communicate their views, perceptions and experiences about their housing environment. The goal have been to provide citizens with the appropriate methods and tools to express and communicate their needs and perceptions and to participate in the urban planning process.

In complementary actions linked to the exhibitions and activities on Virtual Campus workspaces, IUG Grenoble proposed to open the learning program to larger public and to identify potential learning communities.

The first mixed learning community was formed within the Meylan Municipality project studio where French students from IUG Master course worked on OIKODOMOS workspaces with foreign students from EU program Mundus Urbano, planning professionals and Meylan elected officials. Participants shared information, co-operated on the Virtual Campus and used workspaces and repository as documentary support.²⁸ One part of this joint production was developed for the preparatory phase of Istanbul workshop « Proximity ».

Figure 26. Mixed group production for Meylan case study

The public debate « Se former à l'urbanisme- Learning urbanism » associated to the Grenoble exhibitions opening²⁹ confirmed multiple demands from architects and citizens searching for flexible learning support adapted to non-academic audiences. Reactions about the first discovery of Virtual Campus existing structure and functions by some participants on demo sessions presented several interesting parameters to respect in mixed learning contexts

²⁶ Alexander Achberger (Mayor of Svaty Jur), Jan Suflarsky (Mayor of the town Detva), Ingrid Konrad (Bratislava Chief architect)

²⁷ Contacts with University of Malta (Prof. Denis de Lucca), Technical University Kosice (Prof. Peter Pásztor), Mendel University Brno (Prof. Jitka Kominacka), Volgograd State University of Russia (Prof. A. Kalasnikov – rector, Prof. Elina Krasilnikova)

²⁸ Atelier Meylan, programmed on Winter semester 2010-11 and used the corresponding OIKODOMOS workspace

²⁹ see 4.2 Grenoble exhibitions

The analysis of these exchanges and collected information helped the elaboration of a specific pedagogic structure for Housing Learning Module integrated in OIKODOMOS VC.

As consequence of exhibitions presenting results from Virtual Campus and workshops activities, partner universities involved in WP4 discussed also the possibilities to extend the project with the complementary audience.

Preliminary contacts engaged in France by IUG with SFU, OPQU, Maison de l'Architecture³⁰ confirmed the possibility to offer the VC support to professional learners, in the Permanent Education learning partnership framework. IUG will experiment the use of Housing Learning Module as a part of its pedagogic program Formation Continue provided to adult learners in spring semester 2012.

The Dean of EMU Faculty of Architecture suggested a training possibility given to non-professionals within the OIKODOMOS project by University Civic Education Centre. The possibility to collaborate with the Chamber of Architects in Cyprus to use the platform³¹ as a type of lifelong education meeting point in order to train practicing architects as required by UIA Directives.

In Bratislava, FASTU contacts with SAS – Union of Slovak Architects – and partners in different Municipalities present the similar perspectives.

7. HOUSING LEARNING MODULE

The flexibility and potential combination of components and activities allowed by the Virtual Campus can be exploited in a possible adaptation to new non-academic audiences that were not the original purpose of the VC. Informal contacts, progressively systematized, with professional representatives associated in training (tutors of workshops, local correspondents in analyzed sites, consulted citizens) have highlighted specific needs and constraints of this new learners audience.³²

A prototype of the learning module support was composed on the basis of pedagogic experience of blended learning experimented in OIKODOMOS workspaces and joint workshops and uploaded on Workspaces platform³³. Its functions and compatibility have been tested by a small group of teachers IUG and FASTU. Preliminary contacts with other partners university, permanent education operators and professional associations representatives³⁴ show that the module as example of blended learning may be validated and proposed for non-academic learners

7.1 Description

The OIKODOMOS Housing Learning Module is a learning space open to a large target group of academic or non-academic participants. Students and / or non-academic learners, professionals, architects, planners, realtors, associations, citizens could find an access to learning activities related to the Contemporary Housing considered as a part of urban development.

The OIKODOMOS Virtual Campus Workspaces could be used as a learning platform allowing heterogeneous groups of learners to participate to common activities by direct contact or distant, asynchronous way.

³⁰ French professional associations of planners SFU-Société Française des Urbanistes, Office Professionnel de Qualification des Urbanistes OPQU and regional information platform for architects Maison de l'Architecture de Grenoble

³¹ See section 7 describing the deliverable D 12 produced within WP4

³² See section 6 Learning communities

³³ Accessible on <http://arc.housing.salle.url.edu/oikodomos/workspaces/>

³⁴ in France, contacts with SFU, société Française des Urbanistes, OPQU –office de qualification, MdA, in Slovakia with SAS – Union of Slovak Architects, in North Cyprus with Union of the Chambers of Cyprus Turkish Engineers and Architects (UCCTEA), see with Learning Communities section.

Figure 27. Housing Module adapted to the OIKODOMOS workspaces platform

7.2 Educational objectives and functions of the module

The pedagogic model proposes to develop activities and learners competences in following fields:

- Awareness about housing / dwelling in contemporary Europe.
- Discovering issues / basic concepts of urban housing projects (flexibility, functional and social mix, energy efficiency, participation ...)
- Help build the personal documentation, references and repository database (workspaces, compendium of concepts and case study repository)
- Exchanging and sharing of European experiences (personal comments on deliverables, the expertise of other partners in EU)
- Exploring themes of current issues in dwelling / housing, confronted with the themes of flexibility, diversity, effectiveness, proximity....
- Extracting of references from workshops and workspaces
- Introduction to the methodological approach of the project (concepts / site / strategies), transposition to a case study / site on OIKODOMOS VC Workspaces.
- Use / analysis / enhancement of a corpus of examples, references and case studies (Housing Case Study Repository)
- Experiencing an autonomous approach of project or topic in contemporary housing tested in a local context.
- Providing to participants tools to share, compare, assess, co-produce, complement projects by/with other actors (OIKOBlogs, VC Workspaces ...)
- Promoting interdisciplinary teaching practice-based project

7.3 Learning itinerary

A specific learning itinerary combining coordinated blended learning contents is proposed in this Module. Activities capitalizing previous experiences in OIKODOMOS workshops are organized in two possible options:

- One way is to propose Guided Learning Itineraries using examples, sites and selected tasks from completed workshops accessible via Workspaces and Repository platforms.
- The second option allows partner schools or local learning communities to design new tasks and activities adapted to their ad-hoc sites and thematic priorities.

Participants will work in real European professional and academic context, using learning resources produced until now by OIKODOMOS project partners in Spain, Belgium, France, Slovakia, North Cyprus and completed in the future by new associated members. Learning communities received in

each partner school could be involved in different common or joint teamwork activities proposed in this module.

The basic learning itinerary shared by learning community partners is composed with Learning Activity Units (LA) and subsequent pedagogic Tasks (TK) integrated in general pedagogic structure.

Main itinerary and LA sequences proposed in Housing Learning Module:

- LA 1 Preparing the project (TK 1-2BC) setting participants, site selection, development theme...
- LA2 Collecting and organizing Housing data and references (TK 3-4AB-6), site data, housing indicators, urban-housing concepts, mapping territory...
- LA3 Develop an Urban and Architectural analysis and strategies (TK 7-9), Identifying requests, stakeholders, SWOT analysis, spatial and functional constraints, strategic proposals...
- LA 4 Designing a Housing project within its Urban and Architectural dimension (TK 10-12) Conceptual and technical framework, Housing in territory, Architectural dimension, Housing program outline...
- LA 5 Opening the participatory approach (TK 13-15) Critical analysis, Participatory process, Integration of project alternatives from citizens ...
- LA 6 Design for adapted urban housing (TK 16-17), Project proposal, Amended projects...

LEARNING ACTIVITIES/TASKS	DESCRIPTION	DELIVERABLES	MATERIALS, SOURCES	DEADLINES PARTNERS
LA 1 PREPARING THE PROJECT	Field: HOUSING & URBAN DEVELOPMENT Target group: Students and/or non-academic learners, professionals, architects, planners, realtors, associations, citizens Participants, Site, Theme, Tools			URL-LaSalle / St Lucar / IUG-UPMF / FA-STU
TK 1 Setting Participants, VC tools, uses, learning communities - Work program / LA-TK / Timeline / Deliverables	Introductory session with learners	Lists, groups, profiles	http://arc.housing.salle.url.edu/oikodomos/workspaces/index.php/users/participants	(Day 1) (Similar activities/grou developped in partner schools)
TK 2 Site selection / main theme / partners	Selection, data sources Personal summary of perceived critical issues	Materials Themes Lifelong Dwelling, Efficient Housing, Diversity, Proximity, Individual "Manifesto" (1A4 text)	Ghent: (http://arc.housing.salle.url.edu/oikodomos/workspaces/index.php/references) ; Grenoble: (http://arc.housing.salle.url.edu/oikodomos/workspaces/index.php/tasks/view/task_id/96)	Evaluate and comment tutors
Option 1 - guided itineraries G11 Ghent, G12 Grenoble, G13 Bratislava, G14 Istanbul GUIDED ITINERARY G1 1 - G1 2	Personal summary of perceived critical issues	Ghent & Grenoble sites overview, Individual "Manifesto" (1A4 text)	Bratislava: (http://arc.housing.salle.url.edu/oikodomos/workspaces/index.php/tasks/view/task_id/121) ; Istanbul (http://arc.housing.salle.url.edu/oikodomos/workspaces/index.php/references)	(D+10)
Option 2 - ad hoc Site/theme/partners GUIDED ITINERARY G1 3 - G1 4	Personal summary of perceived critical issues	Bratislava & Istanbul site overview, Individual "Manifesto" (1A4 text)		(D+10)
LA 2 COLLECTING AND ORGANIZING HOUSING DATA & REFERENCES	Defining theme, concepts, site specificity			
TK 3 Site Data collection	Urban - Housing Data Mining & processing	see Options 1 & 2		(D+ 2x)
Option 1 - G11 /G12/G13/G14 - downloading from workspaces	Personal summary of perceived critical issues	Groupwork site presentation (Ppt 6 slides)	Ghent (http://arc.housing.salle.url.edu/oikodomos/workspaces/index.php/workshops/index), Grenoble LA3 / TK 4 (http://arc.housing.salle.url.edu/oikodomos/workspaces/index.php/tasks/view/task_id/96)	Evaluate and comment tutors (D+ 2x)

Figure 28. Extract from Pedagogic Structure of Housing Learning Module : LA-TK-outcomes- deliverables-deadlines

OIKODOMOS: WORKSPACES HOUSING LEARNING MODULE

Home Calendar Participants Groups Learning Activities Tasks Sequences Resources Galleries

LA5 DESIGNING A HOUSING PROJECT WITHIN ITS URBAN AND ARCHITECTURAL DIMENSION created by Tucsny, Jan IUG Learning Activity proposing a conceptual and technical framework for projects based on given main theme of intervention.

Learning Outcomes

- The student will be able to discuss the most relevant urban concepts and their designs
- The students will be able to discuss spatial and social patterns of housing which integrate the concept of proximity.
- The students will be able to apply the principles of urban analysis to the site.

Keywords

Workspaces

-HOUSING LEARNING MODULE

Tasks

- TK10 TK10 INSERTING HOUSING INTO THE TERRITORY
- TK11 TK 11 CONSIDERING THE ARCHITECTURAL DIMENSION OF THE HOUSING PROJECT
- TK12 TK 12 PROGRAM OUTLINE FOR AN OVERALL PROJECT

Resources

Figure 29. Transposition in workspaces. Example "LA5 Designing the project" with Tasks sequences TK10-12

7.4 Learning community and learning module management

Module could be organized and tutored within the partnership framework associating academic and non-academic institutions or stakeholders. The quality insurance of learning process and validation of outcomes and competences has to be guaranteed by the University and could associate professional partners acting in the life-long or permanent education.

Activities and pedagogic tasks programmed in the module are designed for multi-cultural, project-led collaborative learning. The ability of Virtual Campus to operate in distance learning, by synchronous / asynchronous way, privileges the cooperation between different partner universities and/or cities supporting the projects, reinforcing the European value of acquired skills and competences.

As the preliminary contacts with non-academic operators suggest and as confirmed by the participatory actions promoted in this work package, the communication aspect and the easy access to knowledge and correct blended information is capital. For this reason, a « tutoring » of learners by assigned teachers is essential, even if the part of autonomous self learning, supported by ICT tools, may be important. The module integrates these functionalities experienced in the Virtual Campus.

One of the difficulties noticed with the mixed learning communities was the language barrier which limits motivation and access to exchanges, in particular for non-academic participants, citizens or professionals. The present basic module integrates several bi-lingual learning components in English / French. Other local versions, translated in different national languages could be progressively completed.

OIKODOMOS: WORKSPACES HOUSING LEARNING MODULE Tuony, Jan | Logout

Home Calendar Participants Groups **Learning Activities** Tasks Sequences Resources Galleries Tutorial

LA42 PREPARING THE HOUSING MODULE PROJECT created by Tuony, Jan IUG

Partners schools and participants experience and customize VC tools, groupwork, learning program, project site selection and learning itineraries.

PREPARER LE PROJET DU MODULE DE FORMATION HABITAT

Les écoles partenaires et les participants expérimentent et adaptent les outils du Campus Virtuel, le travail en groupes, le programme de formation, la sélection du terrain d'études et les itinéraires pédagogiques.

<p>Learning Outcomes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -The student will be able to apply design methods appropriate to housing and urban development design issues (perception of the assignment, site, neighbourhood interconnections... -The student will be able to develop a professional working basis of processes, organisation and communication skills appropriate to their professional practice (eg design and construction) -The student will be able to demonstrate team working skills through personal contribution to a joint presentation -The students will be able to apply the principles of urban analysis to the site. 	<p>Keywords</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -blended-learning -Learning Process 	<p>Workspaces</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -HOUSING LEARNING MODULE 	<p>Tasks +</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -TK1 TK1 SETTING THE LEARNING PROGRAM -TK2 TK2 Site selection / theme / partners / groups 	<p>Resources +</p>
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Figure 30. Housing Module Example of Learning Activity « LA2 Preparing the project » in bi-lingual version

The screenshot shows the OIKODOMOS Workspaces interface for the Housing Learning Module. At the top, there is a dark header with the OIKODOMOS logo and the text 'WORKSPACES HOUSING LEARNING MODULE'. On the right of the header, it says 'Tuony, Jan | Logout'. Below the header is a navigation bar with tabs: Home, Calendar, Participants, Groups, Learning Activities (which is highlighted), Tasks, Sequences, Resources, Galleries, and Tutorial. The main content area is titled 'Learnings Activities' and has a sub-header 'Order by: Id | Title | Author | Institution'. There are two learning activities listed, each with a title in English and French, a description in both languages, and metadata including 'created by Tuony, Jan IUG'. The first activity is 'LA42 PREPARING THE HOUSING MODULE PROJECT' and 'PREPARER LE PROJET DU MODULE DE FORMATION HABITAT'. The second activity is 'LA43 COLLECTING AND ORGANIZING HOUSING DATA & REFERENCES' and 'COLLECTER ET ORGANISER LES DONNÉES ET REFERENCES SUR L'HABITAT'. At the bottom of the page, there is a footer with the text '© ARC Enginyeria i Arquitectura La Salle-Universitat Ramon Llull, Barcelona - 2'.

Figure 31. Housing Module List of blended Learning Activities in bi-lingual version

One possible option for the teaching program management is to use the « guided » learning itinerary which combines different sequences and existing resources produced or capitalized in previous sessions of Virtual Campus activities. It allows also teachers-tutors to adapt the learning program to the particular needs and constraints of non-academic learners.

This flexibility makes possible to offer:

- short-track programs,
- specialized thematic sessions,
- professional knowledge upgrading,
- documentary and thematic references overviews,
- etc,

in addition, or as alternative, to the complete study program compatible with University standards and validated by graduation.

Housing Learning Module transfers, if necessary, existing Learning Activities and Tasks in new sequences. Components could be extracted from different workspaces and used independently³⁵ or be integrated in a specific learning space. Tasks and activities downloaded from completed workshops may compose the frame for a new design studio or a professional knowledge upgrading session. Learning itinerary proposed in this module already selected some components and interactions between existing workspaces and the new learning space. But in this perspective, other combinations are pertinent if conformed to the principle of blended learning.³⁶

³⁵ Example of Housing Concepts or Housing Case Study Repository

³⁶ See for further information “ Learning design with OIKODOMOS Workspaces – The pedagogic model of blended learning” accessible at <http://www.oikodomos.org/resources>

Figure 32. Re-composed structure of blended learning using existing components (Source: ARC Engenharia i Arquitectura La Salle)

Author	Date
Daix, Marie	29/04/2011
Mongodin, Maxime	26/04/2011
Mongodin, Maxime	26/04/2011
Mongodin, Maxime	26/04/2011

Figure 33. Example of possible transposition from Workspace « Proximity » to the Housing Learning Module, LA 4. Bi-lingual version.

7.5 Perspectives

Contacts with external partners and internal consultations on university open learning practice make credible a perspective of larger integration of the OIKODOMOS platforms and Housing Learning Module in forthcoming programs.

In Eastern Mediterranean University in North Cyprus, EMU Civic Education Centre with the support of Chamber of Architects in Cyprus is a recommended partner to open training sessions, based on the use of OIKODOMOS platforms, to non-academics and professionals.. Other collaboration has agreed with and to be organized by the CAT: Chamber of Architects Union in Turkey for their e-learning communities / practising architects with the executive council members of SMGM (Continious Learning Program) in Istanbul and Izmir Branches – still waited to be invited and placed in the agenda at the start of the new year; January / February 2012. The difficulty of the language needed to be solved by the help of professional bodies to help us for translating, summarizing or formulasing the project's main aims, objectives. Thus, the feasibility to implementation of such solution should be discussed with them. Learning Housing Modules may bring a solution if we may bring collaboration with a team that already worked in this area such as from Grenoble and Bratislava .

In Grenoble, IUG will integrate a beta version of Housing Learning Module in life-long education (Formation Continue) study program offered to professionals and adult learners in professional reconversion during the spring semester 2012. Professional bodies associated on debates and definitions of pedagogic aims of the learning module will facilitate the professional validation of competences.

Bratislava FA-STU's contacts with Union of Slovak Architects present the similar perspectives.

8. OPEN PARTNERSHIP FOR BLENDED LEARNING

The Work package 4 (WP4) tried to open OIKODOMS Virtual Campus activities and digital platforms to larger audiences and to offer to extra-academic learners and partners the opportunity to access information and necessary competences to act efficiently in the process of sustainable urban housing.

Exhibitions, contacts with professional bodies, citizens associations, and municipality elected representatives, open learning sessions and debates disseminated the information, accumulated knowledge.

The positive aspect of this dissemination process was an authentic exchange between students and academics and external partners. Exhibitions visitors discovered the contemporary housing problematic, the EU learning programs, the interest to compare experience from Barcelona, Grenoble, Brussels, Bratislava, Istanbul or Famagusta.

OIKODOMOS project and its functionality as « Virtual Campus » were appreciated everywhere and the partnership University-Professionals-Citizens-Municipalities, presented in its European dimension, encouraged to be strengthen in the future. The implementation of the work program showed that the actions have to be closely linked and inter-dependant. No participatory action with citizens is successful if there is not a preliminary information and basic didactics. No effective learning module without preliminary debates and validation by professional bodies... Exhibitions played a federative role with other components of this work package. But there were no simple derivation « from... », but strong interaction « between... » actions.

The blended learning as the basic principle and intrinsic quality of the OIKODOMOS project needs cooperation which should be based on broad partnership.

Some difficulties occurred during the implementation but had generally been overcome and transformed in useful recommendations for the next actions.

We could emphasize some of them:

- Importance of linkage between learning contents or resources and local-related projects, sites, thematic issues,
- Local extra-academic partnership is essential. Municipality support acts positively on citizen and professional audience and motivates the interest for project-oriented learning,
- The association of partner universities, mixed students teams, mixed students-citizen teams, exchanges with other European partners plays as factors of creativity, attractively and success,
- Learning contents and activities have to be organized and tutored by teachers. A combination of distant / on-site lectures, evaluation, presentations is highly appreciated. Viso-conferences with partner universities are a great « plus », even as the evaluations or comments from other European partners.
- To associate citizens and professionals to our learning process, it's important to progress in the selective transposition of OIKODOMOS VC resources in national languages.
- The management of joint activities is sometimes difficult and have to overcome local administrative and logistic bottlenecks. Actions have to be prepared and coordinated largely in advance. The time was occasionally lacking in this phase of development.

Experience of participating schools and members of OIKODOMOS team, accumulated learning contents and resources have to be re-invested in the wider use of the Virtual Campus platforms and existing network of partners.

The question of common or decentralized management, human and financial resources, access to workspaces and the expansion or decline of common activities have to find now new operational answers and perspectives. The solution is probably in the specificity of the OIKODOMOS program, based on open partnership and blended learning.

Appendix 1: Learning communities: the case of the neighbourhood “Plus Ultra” in Barcelona

By Leandro Madrazo, Angel Martín Cojo, Omayra Rivera
ARC Ingeniería i Arquitectura La Salle

As part of the learning activities in the Workspaces “Proximity”, a group of students and teachers from Arquitectura La Salle worked together with the Plus Ultra neighbourhood with the objective of building a learning community.

Introduction

The Plus Ultra neighbourhood, in the district of Zona Franca in Barcelona, consists of a group of low-rise houses constructed by the first settlers in the thirties. In that time, only agricultural fields existed around the first houses. They were built along three streets which were the ones that, at the same time, structure the settlement. From that time on, the neighbourhood has undergone a considerable transformation: in the surrounding fields housing blocks have been built, leaving the old Plus Ultra neighbourhood like an island in the middle of a newly built environment; a leftover from another time, surrounded by modern houses up to 12 stories high. Thus, the exceptional character of the neighbourhood derives not only from the value of the constructions –simple houses, occasionally built by the inhabitants themselves, without much architectural significance– but mostly from the fact that the neighbourhood holds the memories of the people who lived there for the last seventy years.

The city urban planning office has elaborated a special plan to replace the existing buildings, while maintaining some of the spatial and formal features which characterize the settlement. However, neighbours have reacted against this plan since considering that part of their lives would go away with these buildings. Emotional, but also financial interests – discussion on the value of their properties, having to move somewhere else during the time of construction– are behind the neighbours’ claims.

The group of teachers from La Salle participating in the Workspace “Proximity” –Leandro Madrazo, Angel Martín Cojo and Omayra Rivera– thought that the on-going debate provides an opportunity for citizens and academics to engage themselves in a common study on the value and significance of our built environment. In this debate, students –guided by their tutors– helped the neighbours to externalize and communicate their views, perceptions, and experiences about their living environment. Somehow, students played the role of mediators between the neighbours and the city administrators by creating the conditions that favoured dialogue.

Historical Background

The neighbourhood Plus Ultra is one of the settlements that emerged in the periphery of the city of Barcelona during the first decades of the twentieth century, in the middle of agricultural areas and closed to an incipient industry. Plots are between 6 and 8 meters wide, and around 15 meters depth. Houses have from 1 to 3 stories, with the ground floors, occasionally occupied by shops. The original constructions have remained unmodified until our days.

Site plan of the neighbourhood Plus Ultra, Barcelona

An inner street with a Y shape is the central axis of the neighbourhood. At the point where the two branches converge, there is triangular square which has been used for local celebrations. It is the most representative public space.

View of an inner street

The city master plan of 1975 had foreseen already the demolition of the old houses and their replacement by modern blocks. However, the opposition of neighbours has prevented from executing the plan. In the meantime, the neighbourhood has undergone a process of degradation. According to the neighbours: squatters have occupied some of the empty apartments, immigrants have occupied the dwellings of the old neighbours who died or abandoned their place because they could not longer recognize themselves within their living environment.

For satisfying the neighbours' demands, a special plan has been approved in 2005 which is now in process of being executed. According to this plan, the street layout will be preserved but the houses will be demolished and replaced by new buildings. In front of this scenario, a neighbours association claims their right to participate in the decision making process to determine the usage of the public places, the height of the new buildings, the location of the building entries with regard to the street, the distribution of public services, among other issues.

Special plan approved in 2005

The neighbourhood as it stands today

Learning activities

The learning activities and tasks performed by the La Salle group within the Workspace Proximity had the goal of creating a learning community including the participation of students, teachers, neighbours and administration. This experience was shared with other participants in the Workspace Proximity (LA27 TK2 Methods of participation). In order to reach the non-academic audiences we reinforced, specifically in this activity, the usage of social media and also through the OIKODOMOS La Salle blog as well as through a Facebook page which neighbours have created.

The goals of the learning activities carried out at a community level have been the following:

- To collect first hand information from the inhabitants regarding the perceptions and experiences of their living environment
- To provide citizens with the appropriate methods and tools to express and communicate their perceptions of their living environment
- To promote citizens' participation in the urban planning process

To achieve these objectives, the group of La Salle has maintained informative sessions and debates with the neighbours during the five month joint activities. These actions have been disseminated through the social web and through the press.

The calendar and activities which have been carried out from February to June 2011 are summarized next:

- **February 2011:** First contacts with the neighbourhood association: Unió Entitats La Marina, Asociación de Vecinos Plus Ultra. Visit to the district .Compilation and study of public documentation. Preparation of communication strategies with the neighbours.

- **15th March, 2011:** First session of participation within the neighbourhood. Students prepared different questionnaires –printed in big panels- to start interacting with neighbours.

The panels were placed in a room of the community centre to foster a debate among the citizens.

As a result of this meeting, a group of students prepared different strategies to engage neighbours in a joint analysis of the living environment:

1. Approaching people

A face-to-face dialogue is the most direct method to know the feelings and thoughts of the inhabitants. It is important to read between the lines rather than accepting the statements straightforwardly. It is fundamental to give emphasis to the “because” of what it is said in this kind of conversations. Students went to interview neighbours, keeping these guidelines in mind. Then, they extracted some key issues out of these dialogues which were then discussed in the classroom.

2. Relating places

The objective of this activity was to find out where neighbours were carrying out their daily activities: within the neighbourhood and/or in the whole city. With this purpose, students created a map of Barcelona for neighbours to mark their activities. The map was placed on a wall in one of the streets, pedestrians walk. On the right side of the panel, there was a list of activities -visiting family, shopping, entertainment, work, school, and doctor- each one was identified with a different colour. A set of pins with the same colours were provided for the citizens to mark their activities. When this activity was finished, most of the pins were located within or in the neighbourhood surrounding area.

3. Collecting stories

For carrying out the project, it was necessary to find a method to collect the experiences of residents, friends and relatives who visit them. In this case, the communication tool was a photographic montage of the street elevations. Since the streets are too narrow, every building was photographed and then assembled for reproducing the street front. The photograph was placed on a wall in a street, so that citizens could identify the houses –their own or of other people– and write stories about them. The use of photographs instead of drawings made easier the identification of the buildings. At the end

of this activity, we were able to collect a lot of information about the history and the culture of the place. Also, there were some lively anecdotes which helped us to capture the essence of the neighbourhood.

4. Representing the dwelling

The intention of this activity was to represent the dwellings. During our contacts with neighbours, we asked them to draw their dwellings. To get this information, we have done an activity where the participants had to draw their apartments. From these schematic drawings we have been able to realize the grade of importance given to the different parts of the house (for instance, out of what they draw first, out what they draw bigger,...) For architects, this information can be valuable to design the new housing.

These activities were summarized in a blog named OIKODOMOS La Salle (<http://lasalle-oikodomos.blogspot.com>)

OIKODOMOS Blog La Salle dedicated to the learning activities in Plus Ultra

- **March 2011:** Presentation to the neighbours of the conclusions of the previous learning actions. Preparation of a second session of participation. Creation of a Facebook group (OIKODOMOS plus) to exchange information with the neighbours.

Facebook group OIKODOMOS Plus

- **1st April, 2011** - Second session of participation in the neighbourhood.

- **10th June, 2011** - Third session of participation. Presentation of final conclusions to the neighbours.

In this final presentation, the results of the study were shown in a powerpoint presentation using a graphic and written language, which was understandable to laypersons. The presentation was structured in a series of topics (Dwelling, Memory,..) Each topic was introduced with several questions which were supported by images. The purpose of the presentation was to leave in the air some ideas for neighbours to reflect on.

This is a summary of the final presentation:

DWELLING

Issues: What is the most important feature in your dwelling? What do you find better in the existing dwellings as compared to the new ones?

VIVIENDA

MEMORY
 Issues: Which memories do tie you down to the neighbourhood?

COMMUNITY
 Issues: Apart from the problems regarding the refurbishment of the neighbourhood, what do keep people together? What does distinguish this community from other ones?

BEING ROOTED TO A PLACE
 Issues: Do you think that most people who left the neighbourhood would return? What should we do to favour the integration of new inhabitants? Do you know people who keep connected with the neighbourhood although they are no longer are living here?

ARRAIGO

A través de la lucha por la conservación y por la renovación se hace evidente el arraigo de sus vecinos

OFFERING RESISTANCE

Issues: What is worth to be preserved in the neighbourhood? What distinguishes this neighbourhood from the nearby ones?

RESISTENCIA

El barrio ha resistido la transformación urbana; se ha convertido en el testimonio de un tiempo pasado.

PUBLIC SPACE

Issues: What other activities could take place to get a better usage of the public space in the neighbourhood? What activities could take place in the central plaza?

ESPACIO PÚBLICO

Las actividades que se llevan a cabo en el espacio público dan valor al barrio y favorecen el sentimiento de comunidad

ACCESSIBILITY

Issues: Can you name a basic necessity which you cannot fulfil within the neighbourhood? Do you think that shops within the neighbourhood are attractive enough for people coming from outside?

ACCESIBILIDAD

Para que el comercio de proximidad se mantenga, es necesario facilitar el acceso a las personas de fuera.

LIMITS

Issues: Do you perceive the neighbourhood as an island in the middle of the city? In which way the limits that separate it from the city could be reduced or eliminated?

LÍMITES

DENSITY

Issues: Which benefits could bring an increase of the neighbourhood' density? (more houses, more people)?

DENSIDAD

La baja densidad del barrio se manifiesta en el espacio urbano.

At the end of the five months of activity, an article informing about the work done, was published in the newspaper 'El Periódico'.

PROYECTO DE MEDIACIÓN EN SANT S-MONTJUÏC

La vida tras el ladrillo

Un grupo de arquitectos jóvenes trabaja con vecinos de la barriada del Plus Ultra, en la Zona Franca, para ayudarles a negociar su reforma

Lunes, 13 de junio del 2011

HELENA LÓPEZ
BARCELONA

Comentarios (1) Votos: +13 -0 Tweet 3

Vecino desde 1927, Francesc Boix es el más viejo del Plus Ultra, una barriada con aire de pueblo en el corazón de la Zona Franca donde viven unas 100 familias, entre los históricos -como Boix-, los inmigrantes de la primera oleada tardofranquista y los inmigrantes de la segunda oleada, los de los primeros años del siglo XXI. Aquí, un lugar raramente tranquilo con una gran reforma urbanística pendiente desde finales de los años 70, la vida en la calle es muy importante. La gente todavía saca las sillas a las puertas de sus casas bajas todas las noches, para tomar el aire y charlar con los vecinos.

Los impulsores: Los arquitectos Omayra Rivera y Ángel Martín, en la plaza del barrio del Plus Ultra. JONATHAN GRIEVEN

Fue precisamente esa esencia de rara avis, de algo decadente oasis en una urbe cosmopolita como Barcelona la que atrajo a los jóvenes arquitectos Ángel Martín Cojo y Omayra Rivera, quienes, junto a un grupo de estudiantes de Arquitectura, están llevando a cabo un proceso participativo en el barrio con el objetivo de ayudar a sus vecinos a comunicar a la administración «las cualidades y valores que constituyen una forma de habitar propia del lugar y que deben ser preservadas de cara a la reforma pendiente», apunta Martín. En resumen, median entre los vecinos, conocedores de las necesidades del lugar, y la administración que debe emprender su reforma. «La intención es buscar lo esencial del barrio y de las viviendas, las partes de la casa, por ejemplo, que para los habitantes son importantes, aunque a veces no sean conscientes de ello», apunta Rivera.

El barrio del Plus Ultra se compone de tres calles de casas bajas construidas por los propios vecinos alrededor del año 1930. Estos -los que no se han marchado cansados- llevan más de 40 años esperando la ejecución de la mejora que les permita

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